

Inflammasome activation in humans with Crohn's Disease.

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Genetic variation in the NLR family gene NOD2 is the single largest contributor of genetic risk to inflammatory bowel disease. We previously discovered a NOD2 inflammasome that generated interleukin-1beta through caspase-1/caspase-10. We describe here transcriptional activation of NLR family genes with inflammasome and inflammasome-regulating properties *NLRC4*, *NAIP*, *NLRP12* and *NLRX1* in the hematopoietic system in humans with the inflammatory bowel disease Crohn's Disease. In human cells, NAIP controlled expression of a master conductor of inflammation, arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase, a property separate from its described function in inflammasome regulation and apoptosis inhibition. Accordingly, *NAIP* activation in the hematopoietic system of humans with Crohn's Disease was concomitant with activation of *ALOX5*.

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